

METHODOLOGY, PROSPECTS AND PROBLEMS OF TEACHING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN ECONOMICS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the current issues of the methodology, perspective and problems of the use of information technology teaching in the economy, it covers the effectiveness of using advanced pedagogical and information communication technologies in preparing economists for innovative activities, non-traditional methods of teaching, issues of economic education development based on information communication technologies.

Keywords: economic education, innovation, innovative technologies, information and communication technologies, economist, non-traditional education, educational technology.

After gaining independence, our country is developing by choosing its own development path. This path is the path of large-scale reforms aimed at building a democratic legal state, a socially oriented market economy and a strong civil society. The formation of society in the teaching of information technologies has fundamentally changed the role of knowledge in socio-economic development. The main type of economic activity in modern conditions is the development of information and its use for the effective operation of the economy. The main factor of production is knowledge, and this knowledge is delivered through the education system. The modern educational process is based on the concept of well-rounded development of the learner's personality. In order to solve these problems, on the basis of the best practices of educational institutions in the field of information technologies and communications, the organization of scientific research and development, training, retraining and upgrading of skills in strategic and project management, management, marketing is defined as a priority. Accordingly, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and electronic government" No. PQ-4699 was adopted. One of the main tasks of the further development of the digital economy and electronic government is the widespread introduction of digital technologies at all stages of the education system and the improvement of the level of digital knowledge necessary for the modern economy, the improvement of the educational infrastructure, as well as the implementation of the "Five Initiatives" project of the republic until 2022 is to open digital literacy training centers in all regions.

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The gradual development of the economic reforms implemented in our republic and the integration processes taking place in the economy, in addition to the acquisition of economic knowledge from experts, in the teaching of information technology, its object and subjects, the principles of implementation, the world's improved tools in this regard, extensive knowledge of their direct application to financial processes and directly requires having the skills to work on different types of computers. The process of using information and communication and

Internet technologies in the teaching of information technologies increases the curiosity of students and the efficiency of independent work. Together with the use of information and communication and Internet technologies, it provides new opportunities in the field of education, in the study and creativity of students. For the first time in education, a situation arises where a person becomes the main instrument of his future profession using information technology. The purpose of using information and communication and Internet technologies in the teaching of information technology is, on the one hand, to teach students the possibilities of teaching through information technologies, and on the other hand, to familiarize them with the hardware, instrumental and software tools of information technology in education.

Based on the above legal regulations, the use of innovative and information communication technologies in the teaching of information technology is one of the urgent issues facing today's education system. Regarding the issues of using innovative and information communication technologies in economic education, it can be found in the scientific research works of a number of economists, pedagogues and scientists working in the fields of information and communication technologies in the Republic and abroad. In particular, Academician S. Gulomov, B. Begalov, D. Tojiboeva, M. Hakimova, N. Fayzullaeva, I. Mamajonov, S. Hasanov, J. Innovative and information technology issues are highlighted in scientific research works of scientists such as Yoldoshev, B.Safarov, G.Zhukov, P.Matrosov, S.Kaplan, P.I.Pidkasistogo. S. Gulomov, B. Begalov's textbook "Informatics and information technologies" focuses on the effective use of information technologies in the educational system, distance education, and the advantages of D. Tojiboeva's "Economic Pedagogy" textbook focuses on the forms, methods and tools of teaching economic sciences. Also, M. Hakimova, D. Fayzullaeva's "Pedagogical Technologies and Pedagogical Skills" teaching-methodical set and N. Fayzullaeva's, I. Mamajonov's "Professional Education Methodology. The teaching manual "Speech culture of the teacher" reveals the important aspects of teaching methods of economic sciences. S. Khasanov, J. Yoldoshev's educational manual entitled "Pedagogical technologies" directly addresses issues related to modern pedagogical and information technologies that serve to increase the quality and efficiency of economic education. B. Safarov's article on the topic "Actual issues of using innovative and modern educational technologies in economic education" contains current problems of economic education.

At the same time, G. Zhukov, P. Matrosov, S. Kaplan's training manual entitled "Fundamentals of general and professional pedagogy" reveals the main elements of pedagogical technologies. It is known that forming a student as a person, specialist, citizen is one of the main tasks of higher education. The student should be ready for independent thinking, research, communication in the process of solving fundamental and vitally important problems in science, technology, culture and society. Such demand is an important socio-economic task in preparing competitive graduates for the modern labor market. Currently, there is an increasing need for highly qualified specialists with critical thinking skills in enterprises and organizations operating in our country.

- acceleration of society's development;
- transition to an information society, emergence and growth of global problems;
- reduction of the unskilled and low-skilled labor sector, deep structural changes in the employment sector;
- increasing the role of human capital in the economic development of society.

The educational system is one of the main social institutions, an important sphere of personality formation, a historically formed system of educational institutions and their management bodies, which serves the purposes of educating the growing generation, preparing them for independent life and professional activity, and meeting their individual needs for education. One of the priority areas of modernization of the education system and an important task is the modernization of the management model of this system. Management of education in modern conditions is primarily management of the process of educational development. It will be necessary to create a unified system of education statistics and education quality indicators, as well as an education monitoring system

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